

Smarandache Lattice and Pseudo Complement

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce Smarandache - 2-algebraic structure of lattice S , namely *Smarandache lattices*. A Smarandache 2-algebraic structure on a set N means a weak algebraic structure A_0 on N such that there exists a proper subset M of N which is embedded with a stronger algebraic structure A_1 , where a stronger algebraic structure means such a structure which satisfies more axioms, by proper subset one can understand a subset different from the empty set, by the unit element if any, and from the whole set. We obtain some of its characterization through pseudo complemented.

Key Words: Lattice, Boolean algebra, Smarandache lattice and Pseudo complemented lattice.

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§1. Introduction

New notions are introduced in algebra to study more about the congruence in number theory by Florentin Smarandache [1]. By <proper subset> of a set A , we consider a set P included in A , different from A , also different from the empty set and from the unit element in A - if any they rank the algebraic structures using an order relationship.

The algebraic structures $S_1 \ll S_2$ if both of them are defined on the same set; all S_1 laws are also S_2 laws; all axioms of S_1 law are accomplished by the corresponding S_2 law; S_2 law strictly accomplishes more axioms than S_1 laws, or in other words S_2 laws has more laws than S_1 . For example, a semi-group \ll monoid \ll group \ll ring \ll field, or a semi group \ll commutative semi group, ring \ll unitary ring, \dots etc. They define a general special structure to be a structure SM on a set A, different from a structure SN, such that a proper subset of A is an SN structure, where SM \ll SN.

§2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 Let P be a lattice with 0 and $x \in P$. We say x^* is a pseudo complemented of

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x iff $x^* \in P$ and $x \wedge x^* = 0$, and for every $y \in P$, if $x \wedge y = 0$ then $y \leq x^*$.

Definition 2.2 Let P be a pseudo complemented lattice. $N_P = \{ x^* : x \in P \}$ is the set of complements in P . $N_P = \{ N_P, \leq_N, \neg_N, 0_N, 1_N, \wedge_N, \vee_N \}$, where

- (1) \leq_N is defined by: for every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \leq_N y$ iff $x \leq_P y$;
- (2) \neg_N is defined by: for every $x \in N_P$, $\neg_N(x) = x^*$;
- (3) \wedge_N is defined by: for every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \wedge_N y = x \wedge_P y$;
- (4) \vee_N is defined by: for every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \vee_N y = (x^* \wedge_P y^*)^*$;
- (5) $1_N = 0_P^*$, $0_N = 0_P$.

Definition 2.3 Let P be a lattice with 0 . Define I_P to be the set of all ideals in P , i.e., $I_P = \langle I_P, \leq_I, \wedge_I, \vee_I, 0_I, 1_I \rangle$, where

$$\leq = \subseteq, i \wedge_I j = I \cap J, i \vee_I j = (I \cup J), 0_I = 0_A, 1_I = A.$$

Definition 2.4 If P is a distributive lattice with 0 , I_P is a complete pseudo complemented lattice, let P be a lattice with 0 and NI_P , the set of normal ideals in P , is given by $NI_P = \{ I^* \in I_P : I \in I_P \}$. Alternatively, $NI_P = \{ I \in I_P : I = I^{**} \}$. Thus $NI_P = \{ NI_P, \subseteq, \cap, \cup, \wedge_{NI}, \vee_{NI} \}$, which is the set of pseudo complements in I_P .

Definition 2.5 A Pseudo complemented distributive lattice P is called a stone lattice if, for all $a \in P$, it satisfies the property $a^* \vee a^{**} = 1$.

Definition 2.6 Let P be a pseudo complemented distributive lattice. Then for any filter F of P , define the set $\delta(F)$ by $\delta(F) = \{ a^* \in P / a^* \in F \}$.

Definition 2.7 Let P be a pseudo complemented distributive lattice. An ideal I of P is called a δ -ideal if $I = \delta(F)$ for some filter F of P .

Now we have introduced a definition by [4]:

Definition 2.8 A lattice S is said to be a Smarandache lattice if there exist a proper subset L of S , which is a Boolean algebra with respect to the same induced operations of S .

§3. Characterizations

Theorem 3.1 Let S be a lattice. If there exist a proper subset N_P of S defined in Definition 2.2, then S is a Smarandache lattice.

Proof By hypothesis, let S be a lattice and whose proper subset $N_P = \{ x^* : x \in P \}$ is the set of all pseudo complements in P . By definition, if P is a pseudo complement lattice, then $N_P = \{ x^* : x \in P \}$ is the set of complements in P , i.e., $N_P = \{ N_P, \leq_N, \neg_N, 0_N, 1_N, \wedge_N, \vee_N \}$, where

- (1) \leq_N is defined for every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \leq_N y$ iff $x \leq_P b$;
- (2) \neg_N is defined for every $x \in N_P$, $\neg_N(x) = x^*$;
- (3) \wedge_N is defined for every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \wedge_N y = x \wedge_P y$;
- (4) \vee_N is defined for every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \vee_N y = (x * \wedge_P y^*)^*$;
- (5) $1_N = 0_{P^*}$, $0_N = 0_P$.

It is enough to prove that N_P is a Boolean algebra.

(1) For every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \wedge_N y \in N_P$ and \wedge_N is meet under \leq_N . If $x, y \in N_P$, then $x = x^{**}$ and $y = y^{**}$.

Since $x \wedge_P y \leq_P x$, by result if $x \leq_N y$ then $y^* \leq_N x^*$, $x^* \leq_P (x \wedge_P y)^*$, and with by result if $x \leq_N y$ then $y^* \leq_N x^*$, $(x \wedge_P y)^{**} \leq_P x$. Similarly, $(x \wedge_P y)^{**} \leq_P y$. Hence $(x \wedge_P y)^{**} \leq_P (x \wedge_P y)^{**}$.

By result, $x \leq_N x^{**}$, $(x \wedge_P y) \leq_P (x \wedge_P y)^{**}$. Hence $(x \wedge_P y) \in N_P$, $(x \wedge_N y) \in N_P$. If $a \in N_P$ and $a \leq_N x$ and $a \leq_N y$, then $a \leq_P x$ and $a \leq_P y$, $a \leq_P (x \wedge_P y)$. Hence $a \leq_N (x \wedge_N y)$. So, indeed \wedge_N is meet in \leq_N .

(2) For every $x, y \in N_P$, $x \vee_N y \in N_P$ and \vee_N is join under \leq_N . Let $x, y \in N_P$. Then $x^*, y^* \in N_P$. By (1), $(x * \wedge_P y^*) \in N_P$. Hence $(x * \wedge_P y^*)^* \in N_P$, and hence $(x \vee_N y) \in N_P$, $(x * \wedge_P y^*) \leq_P x^*$. By result $x \leq_N x^{**}$, $x^{**} \leq_P (x * \wedge_P y^*)^*$ and $N_P = \{x \in P; x = x^{**}\}$, $x \leq_P (x * \wedge_P y^*)^*$.

Similarly, $y \leq_P (x * \wedge_P y^*)^*$. If $a \in N_P$ and $x \leq_N a$ and $y \leq_N a$, then $x \leq_P a$ and $y \leq_P a$, then by result if $x \leq_N y$, then $y^* \leq_N x^*$, $a^* \leq_P x^*$ and $a^* \leq_P y^*$. Hence $a^* \leq_P (x * \wedge_P y^*)^*$. By result if $x \leq_N y$ then $y^* \leq_N x^*$, $(x * \wedge_P y^*)^* \leq_P a^{**}$. Thus, by result $N_P = \{x \in P : x = x^{**}\}$, $(x * \wedge_P y^*)^* \leq_P x$ and $x \vee_N y \leq_N a$. So, indeed \vee_N is join in \leq_N .

(3) $0_N, 1_N \in N_P$ and $0_N, 1_N$ are the bounds of N_P . Obviously $1_N \in N_P$ since $1_N = 0_{P^*}$ and for every $a \in N_P$, $a \wedge_P 0_P = 0_P$. For every $a \in N_P$, $a \leq_P 0_{P^*}$. Hence $a \leq_N 1_N$, $0_{P^*}, 0_P^{**} \in N_P$ and $0_P^* \wedge_P 0_P^{**} \in N_P$. But of course, $0_{P^*} \wedge_P 0_P^{**} = 0_P$. Thus, $0_P \in N_P$, $0_N \in N_P$. Obviously, for every $a \in N_P$, $0_P \leq_P a$. Hence for every $a \in N_P$, $0_N \leq_N a$. So N_P is bounded lattice.

(4) For every $a \in N_P$, $\neg_N(a) \in N_P$ and for every $a \in N_P$, $a \wedge_N \neg_N(a) = 0_N$, and for every $a \in N_P$, $a \vee_N \neg_N(a) = 1_N$.

Let $a \in N_P$. Obviously, $\neg_N(a) \in N_P$, $a \vee_N \neg_N(a) = a \vee_N a^* = ((a * \wedge_P b^{**})^* = (a * \wedge_P a)^* = 0_{P^*} = 1_N$, $a \wedge_N \neg_N(a) = a \wedge_P a^* = 0_P = 0_N$. So N_P is a bounded complemented lattice.

(5) Since $x \leq_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))$, $(x \wedge_N z) \leq_N x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z)$. Also $(y \wedge_N z) \leq_N x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z)$. Obviously, if $a \leq_N b$, then $a \wedge_N b^* = 0_N$. Since $b \wedge b^* = 0_N$, so $(x \wedge_N z) \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^* = 0_N$ and $(y \wedge_N z) \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^* = 0_N$, $x \wedge_N (z \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^*) = 0_N$, $y \wedge_N (z \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^*) = 0_N$.

By definition of pseudo complement: $z \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^* \leq_N x^*$, $z \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^* \leq_N y^*$, Hence, $z \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^* \leq_N x^* \wedge_N y^*$. Once again, If $a \leq_N b$, then $a \wedge_N b^* = 0_N$. Thus, $z \wedge_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^* \wedge (x^* \wedge_N y^*)^* = 0_N$, $z \wedge_N (x^* \wedge_N y^*)^* \leq_N (x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^{**}$. Now, by definition of \wedge_N : $z \wedge_N (x^* \vee_N y^*)^* = z \wedge_N (x \vee_N y)$ and by $N_P = \{x \in P : x = x^{**}\}$: $(x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z))^{**} = x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z)$. Hence, $z \wedge_N (x \vee_N y) \leq_N x \vee_N (y \wedge_N z)$.

Hence, indeed N_P is a Boolean Algebra. Therefore by definition, S is a Smarandache lattice. \square

For example, a distributive lattice D_3 is shown in Fig.1,

Fig.1

where D_3 is pseudo complemented because

$$\begin{aligned}
 0^* &= 17, \\
 8^* &= 11^* = 12^* = 13^* = 14^* = 15^* = 16^* = 17^* = 0, \\
 1^* &= 10, 6^* = 10^* = 1, \\
 2^* &= 9, 5^* = 9^* = 2, \\
 3^* &= 7, 4^* = 7^* = 3
 \end{aligned}$$

and its correspondent Smarandache lattice is shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2

Theorem 3.2 *Let S be a distributive lattice with 0 . If there exist a proper subset NI_P of S , defined Definition 2.4. Then S is a Smarandache lattice.*

Proof By hypothesis, let S be a distributive lattice with 0 and whose proper subset $NI_P = \{I^* \in I_P, I \in I_P\}$ is the set of normal ideals in P . We claim that NI_P is Boolean algebra since $NI_P = \{I^* \in I_P : I \in I_P\}$ is the set of normal ideals in P .

Alternatively, $NI_P = \{I \in I_P : I = I^{**}\}$. Let $I \in I_P$. Take $I^* = \{y \in P : \text{forevery } i \in I : y \wedge i = 0\}$, $I^* \in I_P$. Namely, if $a \in I^*$ then for every $i \in I : a \wedge i = 0$. Let $b \leq a$. Then, obviously, for every $i \in I, b \wedge i = 0$. Thus $b \in I^*$. If $a, b \in I^*$, then for every $i \in I, a \wedge i = 0$, and for every $i \in I, b \wedge i = 0$.

Hence for every $i \in I, (a \wedge i) \vee (b \wedge i) = 0$. By distributive, for every $i \in I, i \wedge (a \vee b) = 0$, i.e., $a \vee b \in I^*$. Thus $I^* \in I_P, I \cap I^* = I \cap \{y \in P, \text{forevery } i \in I, y \wedge i = 0\} = \{0\}$.

Let $I \cap J = \{0\}$ and $j \in J$. Suppose that for some $i \in I, i \wedge j \neq 0$. Then $i \wedge j \in I \cap J$. Because I and J are ideals, so $I \cap J \neq \{0\}$. Hence, for every $i \in I, j \wedge i = 0$, and $j \subseteq I^*$.

Consequently, I^* is a pseudo complement of I and I_P is a pseudo complemented. Therefore I_P is a Boolean algebra. Thus NI_P is the set of all pseudo complements lattice in I_P .

Notice that we have proved that pseudo complemented form a Boolean algebra in Theorem 3.1. Whence, NI_P is a Boolean algebra. By definition, S is a Smarandache lattice. \square

Theorem 3.3 *Let S be a lattice. If there exist a pseudo complemented distributive lattice P , $X^*(P)$ is a sub-lattice of the lattice $I^\delta(P)$ of all δ -ideals of P , which is the proper subset of S . Then S is a Smarandache lattice.*

Proof By hypothesis, let S be a lattice and there exist a pseudo complemented distributive lattice P , $X^*(P)$ is a sub-lattice of the lattice $I^\delta(P)$ of all δ -ideals of P , which is the proper subset of S .

Let $(a^*], (b^*) \in X^*(P)$ for some $a, b \in P$. Clearly, $(a^*] \cap (b^*) \in X^*(P)$. Again, $(a^*] \cup (b^*) = \delta([a]) \cup \delta([b]) = \delta([a] \cup [b]) = \delta([a \cap b]) = ((a \cap b)^*) \in X^*(P)$. Hence $X^*(P)$ is a sub-lattice of $I^\delta(P)$ and it is a distributive lattice. Clearly $(0^{**}]$ and (0^*) are the least and greatest elements of $X^*(P)$.

Now for any $a \in P, (a^*] \cap (a^{**}] = (0]$ and $(a^*] \cup (b^{**}] = \delta([a]) \cup \delta([a^*]) = \delta([a]) \cup ([a^*]) = \delta([a \cap a^*]) = \delta([0]) = \delta(P) = P$. Hence $(a^{**}]$ is the complement of $(a^*]$ in $X^*(P)$.

Therefore $\{X^*(P), \cup, \cap\}$ is a bounded distributive lattice in which every element is complemented.

Thus $X^*(P)$ is also a Boolean algebra, which implies that S is a Smarandache lattice. \square

Theorem 3.4 *Let S be a lattice and P is a pseudo complemented distributive lattice. If S is a Smarandache lattice. Then the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) P is a Boolean algebra;
- (2) every element of P is closed;
- (3) every principal ideal is a δ -ideal;
- (4) for any ideal $I, a \in I$ implies $a^{**} \in I$;

- (5) for any proper ideal I , $I \cap D(P) = \phi$;
- (6) for any prime ideal A , $A \cap D(P) = \phi$;
- (7) every prime ideal is a minimal prime ideal;
- (8) every prime ideal is a δ -ideal;
- (9) for any $a, b \in P$, $a^* = b^*$ implies $a = b$;
- (10) $D(P)$ is a singleton set.

Proof Since S is a Smarandache lattice. By definition and previous theorem, we observe that there exists a proper subset P of S such that which is a Boolean algebra. Therefore, P is a Boolean algebra.

(1) \implies (2) Assume that P is a Boolean algebra. Then clearly, P has a unique dense element, precisely the greatest element. Let $a \in P$. Then $a^* \wedge a = 0 = a^* \wedge a^{**}$. Also $a^* \vee a$, $a^* \vee a^{**} \in D(P)$. Hence $a^* \vee a = a^* \vee a^{**}$. By the cancellation property of P , we get $a = a^{**}$. Therefore every element of P is closed.

(2) \implies (3) Let I be a principal ideal of P . Then $I = (a]$ for some $a \in P$. By condition (2), $a = a^{**}$. Now, $(a] = (a^*] = \delta([a^*])$. So $(a]$ is a δ -ideal.

(3) \implies (4) Notice that I be a proper ideal of P . Let $a \in I$. Then there must be $(a] = \delta(F)$ for some filter F of P . Hence, we get that $a^{***} = a^* \in F$. Therefore $a^{**} \in \delta(F) = (a] \subseteq I$.

(4) \implies (5) Let I be a proper ideal of P . Suppose $a \in I \cap D(P)$. Then $a^{**} \in P$ and $a^* = 0$. Therefore $1 = 0^* = a^{**} \in P$, a contradiction.

(5) \implies (6) Let I be a proper ideal of P , $I \cap D(P) = \phi$. Then P is a prime ideal of P , $A \cap D(P) = \phi$.

(6) \implies (7) Let A be a prime ideal of P such that $A \cap D(P) = \phi$ and $a \in A$. Clearly $a \wedge a^* = 0$ and $a \vee a^* \in D(P)$. So $a \vee a^* \notin A$, i.e., $a^* \notin A$. Therefore A is a minimal prime ideal of P .

(7) \implies (8) Let A be a minimal prime ideal of P . It is clear that $P \setminus A$ is a filter of P . Let $a \in A$. Since A is minimal, there exists $b \notin A$ such that $a \wedge b = 0$. Hence $a^* \wedge b = b$ and $a^* \notin A$. Whence, $a^* \in (P \setminus A)$, which yields $a \in \delta(P \setminus A)$. Conversely, let $a \in \delta(P \setminus A)$. Then we get $a^* \notin A$. Thus, we have $a \in A$ and $P = \delta(P \setminus A)$. Therefore A is δ -ideal of P .

(8) \implies (9) Assume that every prime ideal of P is a δ -ideal. Let $a, b \in P$ be chosen that $a^* = b^*$. Suppose $a \neq b$. Then there exists a prime ideal A of P such that $a \in A$ and $b \notin A$. By hypothesis, A is a δ -ideal of P . Hence $A = \delta(F)$ for some filter F of P . Consequently, $a \in A = \delta(F)$, We get $b^* = a^* \in F$. Thus, $b \in \delta(F) = A$, a contradiction. Therefore $a = b$.

(9) \implies (10) Suppose x, y be two elements of $D(P)$. Then $x^* = 0 = y^*$, which implies that $x = y$. Therefore $D(P)$ is a singleton set.

(10) \implies (1) Assume that $D(P) = \{d\}$ is singleton set. Let $a \in P$. We always have $a \vee a^* \in D(P)$. Whence, $a \wedge a^* = 0$ and $a \vee a^* = d$. This true for all $a \in P$. Also $0 \leq a \leq a \vee a^* = d$.

Therefore P is a bounded distributive lattice, in which every element is complemented, Hence the above conditions are equivalent. \square

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